

The Challenges that Stakeholders Encounter in Improving Student Behavior and School Discipline in Primary Schools in Cambodia

Hai Sophan

Ph.D. in EAL, Faculty of Education, Arts, and Humanities, BELTEI International University, Phnom Penh, Cambodia

ABSTRACT

Education plays a crucial role in shaping both individuals and societies, serving as a vital instrument for personal growth and social advancement. It is not only essential in Cambodia but across the globe, where the significance of education is fostering positive student behavior and school discipline. The study is chosen 30 participants, in three selected primary schools. This study has been conducted at primary schools, within Kandal province, Cambodia. The chosen participants are the directors, vice directors, librarians, teachers. In this research, I will select these participants to interview, three director, three vice-director, three librarian, seven teachers in one school. The research was conducted through interviews in order to examine participants' perception on school discipline and student behavior. Finding refer to thematic analyze show that the challenges that encountered are parents and teachers are poor collaboration to improve student behavior, and directors and teachers are strongly intervene students who are misbehavior and get mistake. To sum up, all the stakeholders should work as volunteering in an effort to improve student behavior and school discipline, and have regular meeting.

KEYWORDS: Stakeholders, Student Conduct, School Discipline, Parental Involvement, Teachers, Administrators, Community Involvement, Positive Behavioral Interventions, Collaboration, Academic Achievement, Mentorship Programs, Policy Development, Classroom Management, Educational Climate, Conflict Resolution.

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the Study

Education is very crucial in shaping and building people and societies as well, and it is a major instrument for social and individual growth. It is not only crucial in Cambodia but globally, where the significance of education is initiating good behavior among learners and school tidiness. Through education, learners are equipped with information, skills, and values, becoming dynamic and responsive members of society and good citizens (Dalenogare, Benitez, Ayala, & Frank, 2018).

Schools have employed several strategies for increasing student behavior and school discipline in primary schools, including: teachers training, good parent relationship, Counseling and Support Services, disciplinary action (Osher, Bear, Sprague, & Doyle, 2010).

Ministry of Education has employed several initiatives for increasing student behavior and school discipline in primary schools, including: Training for Educators, Involving Parents and Communities

In the last several years, within Cambodia, Ministry of Education there has been a lot of debate regarding how student behavior and school discipline are connected. Schools must balance maintaining a safe and productive school with addressing the underlying causes of the misbehavior as disciplinary difficulties become more common for students. This essay will explore the ways schools can properly manage the behavior of students with discipline and other measures, and the various social, psychological, and environmental factors that influence student behavior. A healthy and happy learning environment can be fostered for all children by teachers through improved

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understanding of the complex dynamics in student behavior and school discipline.

1.2. Problem Statement

Today, the behavior of students in primary schools remains not to the desired standards, and Cambodian school discipline as well (Benveniste, Marshall, & Araujo, 2008). There lacks cooperation among these stakeholders that is the issue in improving students' behavior and school discipline (Njoroge, Nyabuto, & research, 2014). This study seeks to bring forth successful measures in improving student behavior and school discipline in primary schools (Ajowi, Simatwa, & Reviews, 2010). This research has the aim of providing quality of education to improve student behavior and school discipline in primary schools (Ron Nelson, Martella, Marchand-Martella, & Disorders, 2002).

The problem of improving student behavior and school discipline is a complex issue that is prevalent in the majority of schools in Kandal, Cambodia. In the majority of schools, students exhibit an extensive set of behavior problems that may disrupt the learning environment and negatively impact academic achievement. These include such behaviors as disruptions in the classroom, bullying, disrespect to staff, and other forms of misbehavior (Al-Amarat, 2011). Schools are faced with effective ways of improving the behavior of students and discipline without resorting to punitive measures that may exacerbate the problem. The goal is to create a positive school culture where students are safe, supported, and empowered to learn and grow.

1.3. Research Objectives

The main aim of this research is to provide understanding of the optimal ways to improve student behavior and promote positive school discipline.

By identifying the most effective interventions, this study will help facilitate the development of evidence-based solutions to addressing this imperative issue. This research will benefit educators, policymakers, and researchers who are concerned about improving student behavior and promoting a positive school culture. At the end of the introduction, the reader should know what the research purpose is and the significance of the research.

The study's particular research objectives were as follows:

1. To ascertain the challenges encountered in improving student behavior and school discipline in Cambodian primary schools in Kandal province.
2. To explore what has been done to overcome the challenges in improving student behavior and

school discipline in Cambodian primary schools in Kandal province.

1.4. Research questions

The main objective of this study is to identify effective strategies for improving student behavior and promoting positive school discipline. By answering this research question, this study will provide important insights into evidence-based approaches to addressing this critical issue. The results of this study will be useful for educators, policymakers, and researchers who are interested in improving student behavior and promoting a positive school culture. By the end of the introduction, the reader should have a clear understanding of the research question and the significance of the study.

The study's particular research questions were as follows:

1. What are the challenges in improving student behavior and school disciplines in Cambodian primary schools in Kandal province?
2. What has been done to overcome the challenges in improving student behaviors and school principals in Cambodian primary schools in Kandal province?

1.5. Research Significant

This study can be useful to the school principals, teachers, parents or community, students such as:

Offers some key contributions to school principals: The study provides how the principals can easily engage various stakeholders such as teachers, parents, students, and members of the community in managing student behaviour and disciplinary measures, learn to access conflict resolution, relationship-building.

Contributions to teachers: This study provides how teachers create social media for working with the parents of students in order to request or trade the study of students, teacher can learn how to terminate the challenges or how to remove the challenges, provide the successful disciplinary action and school regulation.

Parents/community:

1. To inform in order to be actively engage in improving children's behavior having self-discipline,
2. encourage student to listen to parent, teachers and others
3. parenting or assisting all families create home settings to support students.

1.6. Limitation

This study is limited to directors, vice-directors, committees, librarian, administrators, teachers, NGOs, and students of parents from 3 schools in

Areiksat city regarding discipline practices in primary schools, grades 5 to 6. Data gained analysis is generalizable merely to participants of this study, not

for the generalizability readers can obtain by the qualitative findings (Nelson, 2002).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Direct stakeholders and Indirect Stakeholders Involvement

2.2. Direct Stakeholder:

Director's Responsibility: The director plays a key role in developing the school's culture and climate. Some of the duties are (Daly-Smith et al., 2020).

Vision and Policy Development: The director establishes the vision for students' behavior and discipline. This involves formulating brief policies that outline expectations and sanctions, creating a positive school climate. **Leadership and Support:** By setting an example through good behavior and decision-making, the director sets a standard for both students and staff. They provide guidance and materials to teachers so that they will be able to effectively enforce discipline measures. **Communication:** The director communicates expectations and policies to students, parents, and staff. This assists in establishing trust and helps everyone be on the same level as regards behavior standards. **Professional Growth:** They offer classroom management and restorative practice training for teachers, equipping them to address behavior issues in advance.

Vice-Director's Role: The vice-director supports the work of the director and is more of a hands-on operational leader on a daily basis (Bingham, Nabatchi, & O'Leary, 2005). Their contributions and functions are:

Policy Implementation: The vice-director ensures that policies formulated by the director are implemented at school effectively. They work with teachers and staff members to apply rules consistently. **Conflict Resolution:** In his role as mediator, the vice-director resolves disputes among students and solves problems promptly, promoting a restorative rather than punitive approach. **Student Engagement:** The vice-director is often at the forefront of student-engaging activities like mentorship programs, peer mediation, and extracurricular activities promoting teamwork and

respect. **Assistance to Teachers:** By providing on-site assistance and guidance to teachers with behavior challenges, the vice-director provides a harmonious learning environment. They can also assist in developing individualized behavior plans for students. **Observation and Feedback:** The vice-director constantly observes the classroom environment and provides feedback to teachers. This position as an observer plays a significant role in identifying best practices and those needing improvement (Nettles & Herrington, 2007). **Parents/Guardians' Role:** Parents also play a key role in shaping students' behavior and supporting efforts at discipline. Parents' participation can include building behavioral expectations within the home environment, being transparent with school staff, showing up for parent-teacher conferences, and participating in disciplinary interventions or programs (Patall, Cooper, & Robinson, 2008).

2.3. Indirect Stakeholders (Kyriakides et al., 2015).

Community Members: Local businesses and residents help improve student behavior through provision of resources, mentorship, and funds. **School Board Members:** These are elected members who make policies and offer resources to enhance school discipline. **Education Researchers and Experts:** They study and provide training to teachers to assist them in preparing pupile attitude effectively. **Government Agencies:** These agencies create policies and provide finances to promote positive student behavior and school discipline.

2.4. The challenges stakeholders experienced while improving student behavior and school discipline.

Family Factors: The greatest challenge of discipline among students is family life, i.e., single-parent families. These kinds of families will never find time and money to improve children's education and therefore will generate negative communication with

schools. Further, if parents are not interested in education, this will de-motivate student attitudes and behavior (Sheldon, Epstein, & society, 2002). Teacher Factors: Teachers' workloads and attitudes are also some of the best challenges. Negative attitudes among teachers, caused by burnout or insufficient support, can cause an inefficient class. High workload prevents teachers from establishing rapport with students, which is important in maintaining discipline (Chitiyo, Wheeler, & Education, 2009). Peer Factors: Student relationships may negatively impact students' behavior as students would usually pressure each other into embracing misbehaving. This peer pressure provides a situation in which abuse can be tolerated, and it is challenging to effectively impose discipline (Luiselli, Putnam, Handler, & Feinberg, 2005)

Cultural Factors: Cultural differences exist that produce misunderstanding among students, teachers, and parents, and this makes it challenging to enforce consistent disciplinary practices. Patterns of communication and in cultural values differences can produce conflict while using disciplinary situations (Sugai, O'Keeffe, & Fallon, 2012).

2.5. What has been achieved in the way of overcoming the hurdles in increasing pupil behavior and school discipline.

Collaboration of Schools and Families: Schools are enhancing collaboration with families through creating sustained communication in the manner of meetings, workshops, and newsletters to inform parents about policy and child progress. Active participation allows for early problem detection and co-responsibility for student behavior. Restorative practices focus on the healing of harm caused by misbehavior, making the student accountable, and developing empathy. Family engagement intervention programs complement and enhance parent empowerment, making a system that enhances discipline and enhances student behavior (Meyer & Land, 2005).

Principal-Teacher Collaboration: The principals and teachers are being urged to work together by professional development workshops that equip educators with efficient classroom management methods. Staff meetings offer avenues of regular communication on issues, best practice, and individual matters of discipline. This builds school and school morale among teachers. Open communication channels facilitate instructors to express their needs, while conflict resolution strategies settle differences in a positive manner, which results in a healthy school climate conducive to quality student behavior (Cansoy & Parlar, 2018).

- **Classroom Management:** Effective classroom management strategies significantly contribute to improved student behavior. Clear rules and consistent enforcement provide students with a standard for appropriate behavior. Building good teacher-student relationships results in respect and participation, with students working accordingly. Active teaching techniques such as cooperation and the use of technology are utilized to promote an active learning environment. The aim is to increase academic performance at the expense of disruptions, with a strong school culture where students understand the importance of discipline and take responsibility for their actions (Siregar, Doloksaribu, & Prayuda, 2024).
- By these measures, schools address challenges of student behavior and discipline, creating collaborative partnerships and foster safe and healthy learning environments that enhance students' overall achievement.

2.6. Gap of Stakeholders Involvement in Improving Student Behavior and School Discipline.

Developed Countries

Promoting Student Behavior and School Discipline With Family and Community Involvement (Sheldon, Epstein, & society, 2002), Prevention of disruptive behavior in the urban classroom: Effects of the good behavior game on student and teacher behavior (Lannie, McCurdy, children, 2007), a brief school-based social skills intervention to reduce challenging classroom behavior (McDaniel, Bruhn, & Troughton, 2017), Community stakeholder feedback for development of a volunteer-coached behavioral activation for youth in a low-resource community (Choi et al., 2024). Cambodia

Relationships Between Teachers' Attitudes, Concerns, Self-Efficacy, Intentions, and Behavior to Include Students with Disabilities in Regular Schools in Cambodia (Choi et al., 2024), Strengthening student engagement and empowering teachers to manage classroom behaviour using social work approaches:

A Cambodian experience (Henley et al., 2022).

There are various researchers in developing countries who studied on stakeholders in Involvement in Improving Student Behavior and School Discipline, yet in Cambodia, there are few articles studying about this.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative research design with the Areiksat city of Kandal province as the setting. The sample is 30 subjects who were selected from three primary schools. The subjects are one director, one vice-director, one librarian, and seven teachers from

each school, and they were selected by purposive sampling. The invitation of the director is to know the problems and collaborative efforts with the stakeholders in improving student behavior and school discipline. The vice-director is also invited due to their positions in school discipline and administration management. The librarian's contribution is valuable because they are able to provide information based on students' reading habits, while the seven teachers, with higher levels of education, dedication, and extensive experience, would most likely provide useful insights.

The group discussions will be between the director, teachers, and 6-10 parents to enable discussion of positive and negative behaviors and themes related to discipline (Patton, 2009). To decode data, a qualitative data analysis flowchart will be followed, guided step-by-step (Rossouw, 2003).

For data analysis, a qualitative data analysis flowchart will be utilized, following a step-by-step guide (Ron Nelson, Martella, Marchand-Martella, & Disorders, 2002). Reading the collected data and transcripts, crossing off relevant pieces, and making a matrix will be part of the process. Steps proceed to determine themes and subthemes, ranking highest-priority codes, allocating categories to data, condensing findings in visual format, and producing a detailed report of results, outlining relationships between categories.

Ethics are of the highest priority at every step in the research. Informed consent will be obtained from all the participants to cover privacy and confidentiality,

and to minimize any potential harm or discomfort. Confidentiality of all data will be observed, and all concerned will respond voluntarily to questions raised in the research

IV. RESEARCH FINDING

This research finding is to examine practice, perception, challenges, that stakeholders improve student behaviour and school discipline, what has been done to overcome, how the school principals work together with stakeholders and perceived by 30 respondents of two groups of direct stakeholders and indirect stakeholders in Areiksat city, Kandal province, Cambodia. This review of research aims to explore the role of stakeholders in influencing student behavior and disciplining in schools. By examining the existing state of studies and research, we aim to highlight the significance of stakeholder involvement, both direct and indirect, in encouraging positive student behavior.

Therefore, data analysis connects with five themes. During the course of this dissertation, I used the term of emergent themes instead of using coding data and subthemes in place of initial coding. The five themes are: 1) student behavior, 2) The challenges in improving student behavior,

What has been done to overcome the challenges, 4) School Discipline. Moreover, there were several subthemes found too. The remainder of this chapter is presented in four group emergent themes, which correspond to each of the four objectives of the study. The framework themes and sub themes are displayed in the following graphic.

5.2 School Discipline

5.3 Stakeholders involved in improving student behavior and school discipline

5.4 The challenges in improving Student behavior

5.5 What has been done to overcome the challenges in improving student behavior

V. DISCUSSION

The study showed the main points for research questions between literature and finding that consistent and inconsistent between on Stakeholder Involvement, the challenges, and school discipline.

5.1. Stakeholders Involvement in improving student behavior and school discipline.

Ministry: policy creation, curriculum integration, monitoring and evaluation Teacher professional development. (Training and Coaching, Community and Family Involvement) (Sugai & Horner, 2006).

Schools: intervention and monitoring, staff cooperation, parent relationships. (Early Intervention, Collaboration with Families) (Skiba & Peterson, 2000).

Teachers: establishing classroom rules, modelling behaviour, building relationships with students, cooperative work with colleagues, parent communication. (engage with parents, set regulation, Foster Student Responsibility) (Marzano & Marzano, 2003).

Parent: setting a good example, co-operation with school staff. (building relationship with school) (Sheldon et al., 2002). **Monks:** the education of virtues, mindfulness and meditative practices.

5.2. The Stakeholders improving school discipline

Disciplinary consequence: academic discipline, verbal warning, school labor punishment. (school expulsion, principal referral, detention sentence, in-school suspension, academic discipline) (Sugai & Horner, 2014).

School rule: dress code, punctuality, health and safety special education rule. (adopting punctuality, being quiet, showing respect towards one another, dressing code, cleanliness of classroom, disposal of garbage) (Sugai & Horner, 2014).

5.3. The problems that confronted stakeholders in advocating student behavior and school discipline.

Family Factors: Insufficient cooperation with teachers, neighbors, no model behavior, no adequate time, increase feeling attack. (Single-parent family, poor communication, Parental Attitudes) (Sheldon et al., 2002).

Teacher Factors: Classroom behavior poor, no cooperation, classroom intervention not strict. (Teacher Attitudes, Workload) (Chitiyo et al., 2009).

Peer Factors: Modeling disruptive behavior, gang behavior, drug abuse, deceived attitude. (peer pressure, spoil behavior, drug abuse) (Luiselli et al., 2005).

Culture Factor: inappropriate dancing art, patent display of sexy clothes, disrespect behavior. (Communication Styles, Sexy clothes styles) (Sugai et al., 2012)

5.4. What measures have been implemented to counter the challenges of improving student behavior and school discipline.

School-families collaboration: home visit, social media, regular update, parent workshop, counseling and guidance. (involve parents regularly, repairing

damage, intervention misbehavior, (Meyer & Land, 2005).

Principal-teacher collaboration: providing information, coaching and feedback. (in-service training, regular meeting, open channels, resolution conflict) (Cansoy & Parlar, 2018).

School-pagoda collaboration: creating Buddhist lesson, creating school ceremony, moral education, mindfulness and meditation practice.

Classroom management: define clear rules, structure routine, intervention behavior, positive relationship, slogan words. (Setting Clear Rules, Establishing Teacher-Student, Engaging Instructional Practices) (Siregar et al., 2024).

VI. Conclusion

6.1. Summary

Stakeholders Involvement: Direct stakeholders of stakeholders (school, parents/family, students), indirect stakeholders (ministry, volunteers, NGOs), lack of enough collaboration with parents. **School Discipline:** Existing Schools discipline (academic punishment, verbal warning, school labor punishment, dress code and make up, punctuality, special education regulation). **The challenges:** The limited involvement of teachers and families, peer influence, number of students (too many), disseminating culture (inappropriate dancing/art by foreigner, conspicuous wearing of sexy clothes, disrespectfulness). Improper implementation of school discipline. **To overcome challenges:** The collaboration between immediate and indirect stakeholders (home visit, social media, regular update, workshop and train parents how to address the problem of students), set up counselling room to resolve the issues such as: spread culture, sexy clothing, disrespect behavior, school discipline inappropriately, improve relationship between school-pagoda (regular meeting, to listen to monks advise, ceremony to educate mind, morality of students), improve students respect for school regulation (dress code and make up, punctuality, health and safety, special education regulation).

6.2. Suggestion for further study

Further research should be done by gathering data from other stakeholders who were left out, i.e., monks, NGOs, village leaders, department and ministry education, so that the topic becomes complete, and also activities of students were not observed. To make this research more comprehensive next researchers should research countryside schools.

6.3. Recommendations

The strategies should improve student behavior and school discipline is collaboration among stakeholders:

Regular meeting (Directors ought to meet with parents and teachers to conduct workshops at the end of each semester to support student behavior). School Regulation (Directors and teachers ought to motivate students to enact the regulation, display the regulation by praising and rewarding identify self-regulated behaviors, encourage students to learn from observing others' self-regulation methods). Foster to build relationship (Teachers need to build relationship with parents via home visit, social media communication app, regular update, students, and staff on the school discipline policy)

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